

Press Release

ENSURESEC Cybersecurity Training and Awareness Campaign – Increasing citizens’ resilience against online threats

The launch of the e-commerce tailored cybersecurity and awareness campaign is one of the biggest marks of the final stage of the H2020 project ENSURESEC – End-to-end Security of the Digital Single Market’s e-commerce and Delivery Service Ecosystem. With this full-scale deployment of the campaign, the consortium completes the development of a holistic solution to better protect the whole e-commerce ecosystem against cyber-physical attacks. Besides the training, which aims to raise awareness for potential, but avoidable threats, the socio-technical ENSURESEC solution contains a security toolkit that provides prevention by design, detection and security enforcement, response, recovery and mitigation, as well as situational awareness for critical infrastructures

After 20 months of research and development, the ENSURESEC consortium is in the process of finalizing its work and demonstrating the impact of the socio-technical solution developed in the project. Last January, partners concluded the development of a comprehensive security toolkit for e-commerce platforms, which will be demonstrated soon and offers both suppliers and end customers effective protection for their data and products. Now, the release of the e-commerce cybersecurity training and awareness campaign finally adds the social component to the solution, effectively improving the resilience of the whole ecosystem.

“More and more vendors, driven through the COVID-19 crisis and the pressure of the market, expand their business with e-commerce models. But often enough, the lack of experience and awareness creates vulnerabilities, that even the best technical cybersecurity measurements cannot bridge sufficiently”, explains Almerindo Graziano. He is the leader of the team from SILENSEC, the ENSURESEC partner responsible for the development and deployment of the training and awareness campaign. Under their guidance, a team of experts developed comprehensive training materials, which aim to raise awareness for potential threats exploiting human vulnerabilities and to show measurements for identifying and avoiding those threats.

Over 100 illustrations, an extensive suite of training videos in five languages, self-assessments, textual information and attack simulations are available right now and accessible without any fees on the campaign’s website:

<https://becyberaware.eu>

“The whole backbone of the campaign is the extensive research we conducted in preparation for it”, emphasizes Graziano. “We reviewed user shopping habits, identified vulnerabilities in human interaction on social media and e-commerce, and analyzed a lot of tools, techniques and methodologies in digital marketing to create a campaign, which is both very realistic and easy to follow and understand.”

This work of many months culminates in an offering that is relevant for a broad audience. To reach as many people as possible, not only the videos, but the whole content will be translated to more languages than the currently offered, English, Greek and Italian. In addition to that, the website is accompanied with a social media campaign on Facebook and Instagram, with illustrations tailored to the different audience groups.

Every training on the website is free and accessible without registration. Only for taking part in the study with different attack simulations, ranging from malicious websites to phishing campaigns, the users have to go through an application process. The registration is only necessary to successfully perform the study and is, following the open source idea of the project, not associated with any fees.

Making the awareness campaign open to the public, closes the circle of the ENSURESEC concept, of safeguarding the e-commerce, from online merchant to customer.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 883242

More Information

ENSURESEC Website: <http://www.ensuresec.eu/>

To keep up to date with the latest news on the project, we invite you to follow us on social media:

LinkedIn – [ENSURESEC](#)

Twitter – [ensuresec_eu](#)

About ENSURESEC

ENSURESEC is an ongoing project in the EU Horizon 2020 programme under the topic [SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 - Prevention, detection, response and mitigation of combined physical and cyber threats to critical infrastructure in Europe](#), and part of the programmes [H2020-EU.3.7.4. - Improve cyber security and H2020-EU.3.7.2. - Protect and improve the resilience of critical infrastructures, supply chains and transport modes](#). The project, with 22 partners from all over Europe, has an overall budget of 9.2 Million Euro and has received a funding contribution from the EU of 7.7 Million Euro. ENSURESEC started on June 1st 2020 and will end on May 31st 2022, and it is coordinated by INOV from Portugal.

Press Contact

E-mail: ensuresec@inov.pt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 883242